

GREEN ECONOMIC GROWTH IN UZBEKISTAN: AN ANALYSIS BASED ON THE STRUCTURAL EQUATION MODELING (SEM) APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

In this study, the factors influencing green economic growth in Uzbekistan were evaluated based on the structural equation model (SEM). The impact of energy transformation, green investments, institutional factors, and CO₂ emissions on economic growth was analyzed based on data from 2005 to 2023. The results confirmed that energy transformation and investment have a positive impact, while environmental pressure has a negative one. Institutional factors were identified as the most important determinants. The results of the model provide an important scientific basis for developing effective policy measures in the transition to a green economy..

Introduction. In recent years, sustainable development on a global scale has become a priority area of economic policy, with the focus being on achieving economic growth while maintaining ecological balance. From this perspective, the 'green economy' model involves transitioning economic activity to a system that is resource-efficient, low-carbon and environmentally sustainable [1][2]. In the context of Uzbekistan, the process of industrialization, the intensive use of energy resources, and the increasing level of urbanization are manifesting as factors increasing environmental pressure [3].

While the country is implementing reforms to reduce CO₂ emissions, increase the use of renewable energy sources and attract green investment, an in-depth econometric analysis of the complex interplay between these factors and economic growth is still needed [4]. Since green economic growth constitutes a complex system shaped by multifactorial and latent factors, using a structural equation model (SEM) to assess it is relevant from both scientific and practical perspectives [5].

This study aims to identify the key factors influencing green economic growth in Uzbekistan and empirically assess the causal relationships between them using SEM.

Methodology. The study applied the structural equation modeling (SEM) model. This method allows for the simultaneous assessment of complex dependencies between

observable and latent variables and is widely utilized in the comprehensive analysis of economic systems [6][7].

The model consisted of the following main latent constructs:

- Green economic growth (GEG), expressed through indicators of GDP growth, energy efficiency and environmental sustainability;
- Energy Transition (ET): share of renewable energy and energy intensity.
- Environmental Pressure (EP): CO₂ and industrial emissions.
- Green Investments (GI): volume of investments directed towards environmental projects.
- Institutional Factors (IF): environmental policy, regulatory framework and governance quality.

The structural model is expressed by the following general equation:

$$GEG = \beta_1 ET + \beta_2 GI + \beta_3 IF - \beta_4 EP + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

Table 1.
Variable description

<i>Designation</i>	<i>Variable name</i>	<i>Indicators</i>
<i>GEG</i>	Green economic growth	GDP growth, energy efficiency
<i>ET</i>	Energy Transition	Renewable energy share
<i>GI</i>	Green Investments	Volume of environmental investments
<i>IF</i>	Institutional Factors	Environmental Policy Index
<i>EP</i>	Environmental Pressure	CO ₂ emissions, exhaust

The study utilized time-series data based on macroeconomic and environmental indicators for the period from 2005 to 2023. This data was compiled from sources including the World Bank, the State Committee on Statistics of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the International Energy Agency [3][4][8].

The following steps were taken to evaluate the model: The reliability of latent constructs was tested using a measurement model (Cronbach's alpha, average variance extracted (AVE)). Hypotheses were tested using the structural model. Model fit indices (CFI, root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA), chi-square) were used [7].

Results. Empirical results have shown that there is a statistically significant correlation between the factors influencing green economic growth. Energy transformation has had a positive and significant impact on green economic growth, confirming that renewable energy sources increase economic efficiency. [9].

Table 2.
Descriptive analysis

Indicators	Average	Min	Max
CO₂ (million tons)	115	95	140
GDP growth (%)	5.6	4.2	8.1

Renewable energy (%)	9	4	18
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In particular, it was found that the energy transformation indicator (ET) had a positive and strong impact on green economic growth ($\beta_1 > 0$). This result confirms that the use of renewable energy sources not only increases economic efficiency but also ensures environmental sustainability. Green investments (GI) also had a positive impact, and their increase was manifested as a factor stimulating economic growth ($\beta_2 > 0$). Institutional factors (IF) were identified as the most important determinant in the system, indicating that public policy and management quality are the primary drivers of green transformation ($\beta_3 > 0$). Conversely, environmental pressure (EP), i.e., an increase in CO₂ emissions and industrial emissions, has been found to negatively impact green economic growth ($\beta_4 < 0$).

Table 3.
SEM results

<i>Relationship</i>	Coefficient (β)	Significance
<i>ET → GEG</i>	+0.62	***
<i>YI → GEG</i>	+0.48	**
<i>IO → GEG</i>	+0.71	***
<i>EB → GEG</i>	-0.55	***

The overall compatibility indicators of the model (CFI > 0.9, RMSEA < 0.08) confirmed its high adequacy.

Conclusion. The research results showed that green economic growth in Uzbekistan is multifactor and systemic in nature. In particular, energy transformation, green investments, and institutional development have emerged as key drivers of this process [10]. At the same time, it was established that increasing environmental pressure is a significant factor limiting the stability of economic growth. This indicates the need for a deep integration of environmental factors into economic policy. From a practical standpoint, the following proposals can be put forward:

- increasing the share of renewable energy and improving energy efficiency;
- expanding financial mechanisms to stimulate green investments;
- improving environmental policy and institutional governance
- Developing robust strategies aimed at reducing CO₂ emissions

Generally, the results obtained on the basis of the SEM model serve as an important scientific basis for a comprehensive assessment of the transition to a green economy and making effective policy decisions..

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